

Editorial

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1. Introduction

The teaching and learning landscape is undergoing major shifts that call for the renewal of skills and capabilities. Such skills and capabilities are relevant to different stakeholders (e.g., students, teachers, school/university leaders) and relate to enhancing curriculum design, using technology, and applying inclusive teaching and learning practices to name a few. Moreover, such skills and capabilities not only aim to foster a growth mindset but are embedded in broader discourses about lifelong learning and social justice. Indeed, as Papa (2020, p. vii) emphasizes “what education does offer are the skills and ways of knowing, thinking, and acting to achieve a more equitable, caring, and fair world in pursuit of achieving the ends of social justice. Schooling can empower individuals through self-reflection on their role in society and teach issues of unequal opportunities/privilege and the skills to challenge, resist, and hope.”

This focus on developing an ability to become aware of human culture as well as a focus on moral and intellectual values reflect the concept of lifelong learning (Thwe & Kálmán, 2024). Lifelong learning moves beyond traditional education to include the development of various competencies (e.g., multicultural attitudes) and employment of different modes of teaching and learning (e.g., active learning techniques) among others to capture learning that is available at different times and in different places. Developing such competencies is essential to live in a global society as an active citizen and reflexive agent. Yet, such skills start shaping through formal education and are enabled by pedagogies that activate all these forms of knowledge and skills to be present and integrated in teaching or learning situations (e.g. peer learning; connecting theory with practice, Virtanen & Tynjälä, 2019).

In this light, lifelong learning relates to social justice (Boeren, 2017; Eynon & Malmberg, 2021), namely countries with access to learning opportunities are more likely to learn throughout life. Social justice in the context of education refers to *leaving no one behind* and relates to practices that have to do with content, pedagogy, curriculum and purpose. These practices in turn, call for teaching and learning approaches that enable redistribution of teaching and learning opportunities, enhance participation, and recognize the structural reasons behind marginalization of certain groups (e.g., groups at risk of social exclusion; groups with special learning needs). Moreover, social justice views learning as a lifelong process that “can provide different elements of wellbeing, beyond redistribution. This includes developing the tools to identify, analyse and “problematize” the social, political and cultural structures that support poverty and marginalization, and that represent barriers for people in achieving their desired situations” (Vargas, 2017, p. 10). Thus, social justice in education involves cultivating flourishing lives through processes in which individuals, as knowing subjects, achieve a “deepening awareness both of the sociocultural reality that shapes their lives and of their capacity to transform their reality” (Howard & Maxwell, 2018, p. 532).

Lifelong learning and social justice act as overarching themes of the papers we host in this issue. Specifically, the papers included in this issue discuss elements of social justice, such as gender equity, intercultural awareness, and equitable participation in education and society. They also contribute to discourses on lifelong learning by stressing the continuing development of teachers, learners, and communities. To begin with, the paper *Enhancing gender equity in succession planning for sustainable growth of SMEs in Tanzania* investigates the role of gender equity in succession planning among SMEs in Tanzania. Drawing on multiple data sources, the study shows that although awareness of gender equity exists, women remain underrepresented in succession decisions. The paper highlights the need for educational initiatives and awareness campaigns to support inclusive leadership. Next, the paper *Internationalisation*

in education: Assessing English as a foreign language (EFL) teacher education curriculum, explores the concept of International-Mindedness (IM) and how IM is represented in English teacher education curricula in Egypt. Through qualitative document analysis, the paper shows that IM competencies appear mainly implicitly. To this end, the study calls for curriculum change to better align EFL teacher education with the aims of international education. The next paper, i.e., Integrating digital media in foreign language teaching: Teachers' perceptions of digital competence, focuses on teachers' perceptions and practices regarding digital competence in foreign language education. Based on a survey conducted with primary and secondary school teachers, the authors demonstrate that teachers are aware of digital tools and core digital skills, but classroom use of such tools and skills remains uneven. The paper stresses the need for continuous professional development, better infrastructure, and stronger institutional support to enable more effective integration of digital media in language teaching. Following these discussions, the Teachers' Beliefs Model Questionnaire to Teaching and Learning, is a methodological paper providing a tool for examining teachers' philosophical orientations and curriculum-related attitudes. Using responses from primary and secondary school teachers, the study refines an initial 38-item instrument into a validated 27-item questionnaire covering four domains. The final paper, entitled Investigation of Teachers' Views on Interpersonal Conflicts in Primary Education School Units of the Prefecture of Pella, Greece, explores primary teachers' views on interpersonal conflicts. The study reveals low levels of conflict, with teacher–student conflicts appearing more frequently than conflicts among staff or with school administration.

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